

THE BOOK OF KNOWLEDGE OF IMPRACTICAL MUSICAL DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a set of three interactive sound objects, collectively titled the Book of Knowledge of Impractical Musical Devices. Loosely based on an early 13th century Islamic engineering handbook, the instruments were designed to adhere strictly to a set of design constraints. In doing so, the resulting designs explore the role digital musical interfaces can play in interrogating our relationship to media. I will describe the design and development of the instruments, including technical details and conceptual background, particularly focusing on how the project designed for and with the selected constraints.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Book of Knowledge of Impractical Musical Devices is an artistic research and design project that explores the role that sound interfaces can play in revealing the fundamental characteristics of digital media. This paper will present the three musical devices and accompanying materials that form the artwork. Each of the devices is limited in certain ways, and can be seen as the result of a constraints-led design process. These constraints include time, place, and impermanence - the limitations placed on these characteristics led to final outcomes that raise questions about sound, technology, and our relationship to media.

I will therefore describe the conceptual background of the project, provide details of the design process and the resulting instruments, and discuss some implications of the work.

2. BACKGROUND

In the early 13th century an Arabic engineer known as al-Jazari wrote a book entitled *The Book of Knowledge of Ingenious Mechanical Devices*, in which he detailed some of his numerous designs undertaken in the service of a king [1]. These include a vast array of hydro-powered clocks, automatons, serving mechanisms, perpetual flutes, and robotic musical instruments. The designs are all described in (sometimes excruciating) detail.¹ In the introduction al-Jazari writes that he was motivated to pass on

¹ "The scribe turns on the axle when the big pulley turns. The three pulleys are inside the dome above a plate and the strings of the weight and the ball pass through two holes in this plate. The float is then placed on the surface of the water in the trough and the dome is placed over the

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his knowledge to others who may want to build similar things:

So I assembled the divisions that they had separated and put forth branches from roots where they had been correct, and devised specimens which worked splendidly, light internally and externally. And when I found difficulty such as to lengthen the journey I hated [the thought] that my diligence might go the ways of the wind and that the trace of what I had made might be woven into the tapestry of the night without morning. So my soul asked of me to pass on a record of that to [someone] whom I would appoint to unroll his parchment and [whom] I desired to instruct. (p. 15)

This text is generally seen as the first recorded example of a number of engineering and material design concepts, from plywood and camshafts to robotic musical systems. It thus provided the inspiration for a new Book of Knowledge, focused on musical technologies.

2.1 Sustainability and Music Computing

In addition to sharing the original Book's desire for spreading knowledge, the grounding of this project enabled it to look deeply at how music and sound technology can reflect our media ecology more generally. Sonic technologies are built on a long history of exploitation and injustice [2, 3], and contain an embedded political ecology that guides the way they are used [4, 5]. The modern shift towards the digital domain in sound has made this even more clear, as the technologies involved (and problematic issues contained therein) now overlap significantly with computing more generally. The materials and processes required in designing and manufacturing a sound-making device are now in many ways the same as creating a computer or smartphone [6], including the extraction of rare earth minerals [7], the use of culturally biased software tools, and the gender divide between "design" and "assembly" [8].

Sound technology design tends to bias towards offering users *more*. There is an assumption that sonic technology should be endless and seamless. Sound can be recorded, revisited, edited "non-destructively", and endlessly reproduced (terms with significant gender implications [4]). Higher sample rates promise more detailed reproductions with the apparently meaningless tradeoff of disk space. Sample libraries are measured in previously

trough; of necessity the ball descends into the centre of the float, which supports it. The string of the ball is slack until the weight sinks and tautens the string of the ball. Then the scribe is placed..." p. 55

unimaginable gigabytes. Modern sound design tools offer the ability to record thousands of hours of audio on limitless tracks with countless plugins and infinite automation points. Sonic technology is a cornucopian playground.

This so-called Cornucopian Paradigm [9] is well integrated into all computing technology. In the context of design, the Cornucopian Paradigm is both an imperative to design for ever-increasing consumption (of data, storage, hardware, tracks, plugins, etc) and the driving force for this escalation. As a simple example, when people get more internet bandwidth, they demand more bandwidth-intensive media, which requires even more bandwidth. These assumptions have been analyzed from a sustainability computing and HCI perspective, with a number of designers and researchers suggesting "limits" based approach [10] in response.

2.2 Constraints Based Design

This project can thus be seen within the context of constraints-based design, which both explores the potential for constraints to be embraced as a fundamental part of the creative process as well as forming a political stance with regards to designing computing technology [11–15]. In contrast to the Cornucopian Paradigm, constraints-based design should be understood as an opposing recursive design practice: to design with less for less. In this sense, constraint-based design is not simply about designing within constraints (since all design must be constrained by its intended or appropriate use, materials, and context) but about designing with a constraint to produce a need for more constraints.

To address these concepts I introduce a set of sound-making devices that engage directly with limitations, with the aim of both metaphorically and concretely reckoning with the issues they contain - embracing constraints in a move towards a more socially and technologically sustainable future.

2.3 Sound Art and Experimental Musical Instrument Design

The work presented here draws on and inherently references a large body of artistic work, specifically with regards to sound art and experimental musical instrument design. There are clear echoes of previous work in auto-destructive art, for example, which has been explored notably in sound by William Basinski with *The Disintegration Loops* [16], by Christian Marclay with his *Record Without a Cover* [17], and perhaps most famously by Alvin Lucier with *I'm Sitting In a Room* [18]. All of these works looked at the aesthetics of destruction, embracing the imperfections that are gradually amplified by time, revealing the underlying characteristics of the materials and spaces involved in creating and listening to the original sound. This concept has been contextualized as a form of palimpsest [19], with layers of destruction and creation each becoming embedded with artistic and political meaning [20].

The *Book of Knowledge* project gestures also towards Chion's writings which describe how sound is completely

reliant on and illustrative of time [21], because listening back to a sound requires inhabiting the same amount of time as it took to record it. While visual media can be perceived at a glance, a hard drive full of sound recordings could take hours to listen to, if not significantly more. The act of recording a sound is an attempt to break the continuation of time, on the assumption that we will one day be able to simply 'make' the time to listen to it again. As such the project aligns with other sound work that engages with alternative approaches to time, such as Ellen Fullman's *Long String Instrument*, John Cage's *As Slow As Possible*, and Jem Finer's *Longplayer*.

There are connections in this work also to experimental and artistic design projects, perhaps most notably the so-called *Slow Design* movement [22, 23]. That approach often uses physical interfaces to interrogate our approach to media and interaction through alternative designs. The elements of the *Book of Knowledge* that draw upon both personal media and location share a particular lineage to projects such as the *Memory Tracer* [24] and *OLO Radio* [25].

More broadly, in terms of musical instrument design this work aligns strongly with Magnusson's analysis of affordances and constraints [26] forming "two sides of the same coin", in this case with the work leading with constraints that then lead to specific affordances.

2.4 Frictional Tendencies and Research through Design

The development of this work responded to no user-centered research or traditional design thinking methodology but rather privileged the creation of functional artifacts that could then be used and analyzed on their own merits. The "results" of this design process are the instruments themselves, the sounds they contain and produce, the questions they raise, and the behaviours they encourage or punish. In retrospect this can be characterized as something of a *Research through Design* approach [27]. While the aim of the project was always to create finished, polished instruments, I would like to resist the temptation to propose that they can be used *for* something, particularly in any sort of commercial sense. This aligns with Pierce's concept of "frictional tendencies" in alternative designs, in which the challenging designs can be seen as mechanisms for generating knowledge precisely because they resist progressional framings [28].

2.5 A Note About Time

Whilst it would be tempting to build a narrative in which this project was developed in a linear and entirely rational manner, starting with a research topic and design concept, followed by designed artifacts and concluding with this paper, I would like to draw on the work of Desjardins and Oogjes, who argue that linear temporal narratives of *Research through Design* projects can be unhelpful at best [29]. Realistically this project can be traced as far back as 2015² and involved a number of what Desjardins and

² a text message from my wife Kristina in 2015: "A random potentially cheesy idea for an artwork - you create something in a digital format (it

Figure 1. The three impractical devices

Oogjes might refer to as "pauses" and "transitions". The design work described here was almost entirely completed well before my transition to full-time academia, and should be contextualized as forming part of my practice at the time as a self-employed artist. As such the project was funded by an artistic grant from Creative Scotland, and took the form of artistic practice with the stated goal of producing artwork:

For this project I propose to take *The Book of Knowledge of Ingenious Mechanical Devices* as an inspiration for a period of development focused on building a series of musical instruments for live performance which challenge contemporary notions of digital music. Much like Al-Jazari's approach, my own work often uses and subverts modern technology, and the technical tools used are secondary to the concept and creative outcome. The project will therefore involve the development of digital, mechanical, and otherwise electronic musical instruments, with the primary focus not on technological advancement but rather on pushing boundaries of interaction, design, musicality, and play. (*from application to Creative Scotland for £8600 funding, submitted 2017*)

Many of the disparate pieces that form the argument in this paper (particularly with regards to sustainable HCI and cornucopian design) were only assembled in retrospect after learning how the work reflected these concepts. Nevertheless I would argue that this allows for deeper reflection and meaningful knowledge to be explored precisely because of (and not despite) the temporally non-linear aspect of how it was designed.

3. DESIGN PROCESS

The design process described in this section resulted in the creation of three instruments ("volumes"), which to-

could be a digital piece of music or a game or a video) and release it to the world, but it should have a built in ability programmed into it somehow to slowly decay the more it is used/listened to etc like a physical analogue piece of media. Maybe it's been done before or maybe it's cheesy but I quite like it as an idea"

Figure 2. The abandoned radio station sampler

gether with the accompanying resources formed the finished project. These three volumes were as follows:

- Volume 1 - **A Day That Will Never Happen Again:** A rhythm generation instrument that exclusively uses sounds recorded on a single day.
- Volume 2 - **Here you are, you are here:** A granular synthesizer with a built-in GPS monitor which changes the sound parameters based on current location.
- Volume 3 - **Everything You Love Will One Day Be Taken From You:** A listening device that simultaneously plays and destroys the only copy of a sound.

3.1 Early prototyping

The early design phase of the project involved sketching and prototyping a number of different ideas, all of which were attempting to link conceptually to the original al-Jazari text and apply a fundamental constraint to the musical interaction. Other ideas that did not end up being taken further included a CCTV-based instrument which would access unsecure cameras on the internet and use them to generate sound, a randomized radio-station sampler, and an air-quality synthesizer, among others. While it is unnecessary to delve into these abandoned designs, they are worth mentioning to emphasize the non-linear approach to the design process.

3.2 From cardboard box to finished enclosures

The physical design of the instruments was a three step process, starting with cardboard boxes (this included some abandoned prototypes) before moving to generic wooden enclosures for testing the interface elements. The final devices took the form of three medium-sized plywood enclosures as a gesture to al-Jazari's use of plywood in the 12th century. These were designed together in collaboration with artist and designer Tommy Perman and included abstract illustrations representing the concepts and processes contained therein. A book motif was adopted, with the three instruments designed to be able to stand on a shelf.

3.3 Three settled designs and their constraints

What follows is a short description of each of the three instruments together with a summary of what constraint they were specifically looking at enacting. I will avoid deep technical descriptions - the details are all available on the project website³ and the technical implementation is not the focus of this paper.

3.3.1 Volume 1

The sound engine in this instrument is a sample sequencer which takes 10 sound files at a time and organizes them into a rhythmic sequence according to a number of different parameters. It runs on a Pure Data patch using a Raspberry Pi and a Teensy microcontroller.

The instrument contains a sound library that was recorded entirely on a single day. I brought a sound recorder around with me on an ordinary Sunday, recording the morning routines (making coffee, walking the dog) as well as a family outing to the beach, running errands, and eventually turning off the lights in the home. These recordings were then edited into a library of 124 sounds and loaded into the device. The core limitation in the instrument is the passage of time. In order to achieve this a real-time clock (RTC) chip is included to keep track of the current date in the Pure Data patch. With each passing day most of the parameters are changed, most notably the selection of sounds loaded into the sequencer - 10 different sounds are selected at random every day. This means that each day that the instrument is used will result in a different combination of moments from the original day.

The front panel of the instrument contains a button for starting and stopping playback, and four analog controls - rate (similar to "tempo"), length (in percentage of the sound file being played back on each step), steps (2-30 possible sequence steps), and "other". This final knob represents a number of different parameters combined together, with the specific mapping also randomized each day.

The result is a device that creates a very different rhythmic representation of the original day each day it is used. It is difficult to calculate the exact odds but given the number of randomized parameters it is extremely unlikely for the instrument to act in the same way on two different days.

3.3.2 Volume 2

This device is a location-based granular synthesizer. A single sound file (a recording of my son as a toddler playing piano) is loaded into a granular engine running in Pure Data on a Bela. A GPS module on the instrument relays location data, via a microcontroller, into the Pure Data patch and sets a number of the parameters of the granular synthesizer. Three parameters are left to user control - the playback triggering (with a button), volume, and pitch of the grains. Other settings such as grain length, density of grains, grain direction, grain location, and various randomness parameters are all mapped to the GPS settings which are accurate to within approximately one square meter.

Figure 3. Outside with Volume 2

The design constraint placed on this instrument is obviously location - the instrument will sound different everywhere in the world. The use of granular synthesis in particular to apply this constraint implies that the sound has been split apart and spread around the world, and it is impossible to hear every combination of parameters. Some grains are effectively lost.

3.3.3 Volume 3

The interface for this device has a single accessible button labeled "Play/Destroy". Inside the box is a Bela micro-computer, an input for a microphone, a hidden button, and a pair of surface transducers which make the enclosure vibrate to generate sound in place of a speaker or headphone output.

Pressing and holding Play/Destroy will play a recorded sound on a loop for as long as the button is held down. Each time the sound is looped a small glitch is introduced. These glitches are written permanently to the memory of the microcomputer, overwriting the original recording. The longer the listener holds down the button, the more distorted the sound will become. If the button is pressed again at a later time, the sound will remain distorted and the glitching process will continue. Gradually the sound will transform into a sort of white noise, which then fades away to nothing. As the button label implies, playing the sound will simultaneously destroy that sound permanently.

This is an instrument that explores impermanence as a constraint. It forces the listener to confront the impermanence of media (among, perhaps, other things) with each button press. In order to achieve this limitation, it is crucial for the sound in the device to be the only copy of that sound recording in existence. Thus to record a sound, the user must open the box, plug in a microphone and press the hidden button. This process is deliberately challenging, to encourage listening rather than recording new sounds.

Similarly, the playback of the sound provides an opportunity to bypass the core values of the device. A headphone output would be an easy location to recapture the audio before it disappears, simply by connecting it into an external recorder. From a design standpoint this is something that should be discouraged at least, though of course there is a limit to how far this can stretch - at a certain point any audible sound will always be capture-able by someone moti-

³<http://www.impracticaldevices.com>

Figure 4. Volume 3

Figure 5. The Book

vated enough to do so. However this requirement nevertheless led to the use of surface transducers, which make the entire object vibrate in order to generate the sound (thereby avoiding any easily accessible hardware audio outputs). This has the added benefit of reinforcing the feeling of the sound as a material which is being destroyed.

The actual act of destruction must also be considered - what is the best sonic method for killing a sound? Initial explorations of this design suggested that adding noise to a sound has the somewhat surprising consequence of framing the original recording, much like the surface noise of vinyl, helping the ear focus on the original sound and (perhaps counterintuitively) making it clearer. It will eventually, of course, disappear, but the listening process is simply unsatisfying. A more effective method of destroying was developed using wavetable playback to achieve the feeling of a sound being used again itself - slicing tiny pieces out of it and place them somewhere else, reversed, or pitched up, slow down a section momentarily before jumping to the end for a few milliseconds, and then continue where you left off. Turn the sound inward, break it apart, jumble the memory of the moment until you can't remember what it sounded like.

In order to achieve this effect a second array is created that represents time, which is used to drive the playback of the recorded sound. This is essentially a graph that begins as a line running from 0 to 1 over the same length of time as the source sound. Applying this graph to the audio file results in a linear playback of the sound - this is known as a wavetable.

Adjusting the wavetable to be something other than a diagonal line introduces variability into the playback of the sound file. If a section of the line has a negative slope then the corresponding section of sound will play backwards. Sharp slopes will play the sound file more quickly, and a horizontal line will stop playback entirely. All of the resulting sound is still being generated from the original source media - introducing a number of "errors" to the wavetable can be compared to cutting up and re-assembling a photograph.

In order for the destruction to be permanent, when the audio is played back the output is routed to overwrite the original file with a short delay (to allow for the playback and overwriting to happen simultaneously). This method

for making the destruction of the sound permanent can only occur while the sound is being played back, since it is the sonic output that is being stored into the array. The listener therefore hears the destruction as it happens.

3.4 Spreading Knowledge

As mentioned earlier, the project work did not have any intended outcome in terms of developing the instruments further for sale or distribution. This was both an artistic and political stance, in terms of a desire to avoid notions of capitalism and growth in a project about limitations and constraints. In keeping with the inspiration from the original Book of Knowledge, the project output instead focused on documentation and the spreading of knowledge. Therefore all of the code, technical information, conceptual background in the form of essays, and the funding application for the project were made available on a dedicated website.⁴ This also formed a crucial part of the project in terms of linking it to the original Book of Knowledge by al-Jazari, which was primarily a method of spreading detailed information about his work. While it may be difficult to speculate on al-Jazari's motivations for this, in my own case this formed an integral part of the concept of the project: spreading knowledge as a form of techno-political critique.

Nevertheless, after a number of requests for some kind of tangible object representing the project, the contents of this website were also made into a dedicated self-published book that could be purchased at cost.

4. DISCUSSION

The application of constraints to the design process transformed what were essentially standard audio systems into something fundamentally different. The underlying audio engines in all three of the instruments are in no way unusual - they are effectively a sample sequencer, a granular synthesizer, and a looper. These were custom built in Pure Data for the purposes of this project, primarily due to technical requirements, but the resulting engines can all be used without the constraints at all in order to achieve

⁴ <https://www.impracticaldevices.com/>

more standard approaches to sound manipulation. The constraints resulted from the integration of these sound engines into physical devices which naturally limited their interactive potential. In Volumes 1 and 2, for example, there is no technical reason why the sounds that are loaded into the buffer could not be changed (and indeed, anyone who downloads the code can and should do so). However running the code on Raspberry Pi devices with no screen or keyboard attached forces the player to interact only using the available controls. Thus the first layer of constraints come simply from what controls are made available to the player. Some of my work following this project has explored how constraints can be applied to the same engine by exposing different interface elements in this way [30]. This type of approach can also be seen in other creative fields that implement constraints, such as the alt.ctrl game design community [31, 32], where in many cases a relatively straightforward digital game design is queered through the implementation of a somehow problematic interface.

In several cases the implementation of a constraint resulted in a cascading set of understandings and dependencies. One unintended consequence of the location-based synthesizer in Volume 2 arose from the use of the GPS sensor. It had not occurred to me when conceptualizing the instrument that the sensor would need direct line-of-sight with several satellites in order to triangulate a position. Modern telephones use a variety of methods to overcome this limitation, giving the impression that GPS location can work indoors, but a GPS sensor alone is not capable of this. It was only after several days of debugging that I realized that this particular instrument would only work outside (and without too many tall buildings around). Subsequent development and testing of the instrument therefore involved constant trips between my studio and the nearest open space outside I could find. In practice a secondary consequence of this is that it needs to be battery powered.

Using the daily sound rhythm generator (Volume 1) resulted in an surprising sense of the passage of time. Each day that I use this instrument, the memories of that previous day - an utterly unremarkable and yet totally precious set of moments - are shuffled and presented back to me in new configurations. In some ways this reflects my own imperfect and shifting memory of that day (or indeed, any day). More poignantly, the instrument becomes something of a meditation on the difference between that day and today, the day I'm listening and playing. That difference is growing steadily larger, but the day contained in the instrument is static. The sounds of that day will never happen again, and it is growing ever more distant. The design constraints generate this emotional power for me, that I can access and embody by playing the instrument.

When I completed the construction of the three instruments I brought them home for occasional explorations in the snatched moments I had between caring for a young toddler and newborn baby. I was setting up Volume 3, the sound destroyer, for testing one day in the summer of 2019 with a microphone when my son approached and asked (not remembering the word for 'button'): "can I press the

Figure 6. Play/Destroy

beep?"

I recorded this question, using the hidden button inside the device, just before his pudgy finger pressed down on the Play/Destroy button, triggering the playback of his voice on loop. "Can I press the beep? Can I press the beep? Can I press the" - but on each loop a small glitch interrupted the playback. The sound was already disappearing, the moment had passed, and he had lost interest. He released the button and the sound stopped. By this stage in the project I had run the sound destruction system probably hundreds of times with dozens of different sounds in order to ensure the permanence of destruction. I had felt myself become fairly jaded by the concept and had assumed that I was prepared for a moment like this. I most certainly was not prepared. I was suddenly struck by the weight of a single moment stored in the device, that listening to it again will also remove it from existence. The sound exists as a set of data points in a buffer on a chip in the device, but any attempt to listen back to it will also irreversibly change it. The moment instead lives on more strongly in my memory - much more so than anything else that day or any number of moments since, including things I have recorded or photographed. The instrument effectively breaks the concept of a recording as something static that can be revisited at any point without considering how one listens, perhaps going some way to realigning with Chion's concepts of time and sound. As such it forces me to confront how I use media as a form of escapism, recording sounds and photographs and videos on the assumption that they are captured and can be revisited at any point. It's ok, I don't need to pay too close attention now, I'll watch the video later.

5. CONCLUSION

Immediately after finishing the Book of Knowledge project I accepted a job in another country and moved away from Scotland. I left the three devices in the care of friends, on the understanding that I'd be back soon to organise some kind of shipment. The pandemic struck, I stayed away for longer than expected, and eventually I found a different position in yet another country. I moved again, and three years after building them I finally managed to get the devices shipped to my new home in Sweden. The three boxes now sit proudly on a shelf above the desk where I am typing this essay.

When they arrived I excitedly plugged in the first vol-

ume, and much to my amazement it worked immediately, generating rhythms as if nothing had changed. I was transported once again to a day with an the early morning coffee in my kitchen, the jingle of a dog collar, a snippet of a windy beach. The second volume turns on but I feel uneasy about bringing it outside. Perhaps the intervening years have made me more cautious. The third volume, Everything You Love Will One Day Be Taken From You, is still on the shelf, the "Play/Destroy" button pointed directly at me. I have not yet switched it on. I don't know if it still works, if the sound that my son recorded six years ago is still stored on the little computer in that box, partially destroyed from pressing the button to hear his own voice. It's probably there, waiting to be heard and further destroyed.

And so the device sits, containing both a moment in time and space and the potential to play it back and remove it forever. It is primed to enact all of the decisions that went into the design, from the references to auto-destructive art to the embodied critique of the political ecologies of sonic technologies. It contains a set of hundreds of thousands of numbers which, when played back very quickly and amplified, I would recognise as a representation of the sound that occurred one morning several years ago. It has a button that can take me back there. I could just press it.

I think I can remember the moment that is contained in the box, though I have completely forgotten countless others from that time and since. Knowing that it is in there makes me reckon with the time that has elapsed since, and it reminds me to listen with care, to be aware of the destruction that I contain and inflict.

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